

FEATURES OF SUBSTANTIVE PHRASES IN RUSSIAN AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7634261>

Annotation: This article provides information on how to use phrases in Uzbek and Russian languages and their usage. In addition, the types of word combinations and the order of their formation are also discussed. Similarities and differences of word combinations in Russian and Uzbek languages are also explained through examples.

Key words: word combination, grammatical connection, syntactic structure, speech unit, simple word combination, complex word combination.

A word combination is a syntactic structure formed as a result of joining two or more independent words based on a subordinate grammatical relationship (adaptation, control, or agreement) and indicates the name of things and events in existence. Any combination of words is formed from the combination of more than one independent word, is formed and consists of two parts - the governing part and the subordinate part: higher information (higher - the subordinate part, information - the governing part). Word combinations are divided into simple and complex types according to the composition of their components. A phrase whose components are equal to one form of a word is a simple phrase: like a wandering bird, twenty houses, run fast. Compounds whose components or one of them consists of more than one word or word combination are called complex word combinations. For example, a highly educated specialist (highly educated is a subordinate part, specialist is a ruling part). Depending on the word group of the governing part of the composition, there are 2 types of word combination: noun phrase and verb phrase. A noun phrase is a word phrase (all students, beautiful village, etc.) expressed by a word belonging to a category other than a verb (noun, adverb). A verb phrase is a word phrase expressed by a verb in the possessive part (such as to walk around the garden, to read a book, to walk quickly). According to the syntactic function of the subordinate word in its composition, there are 3 types: a qualifying phrase, a complementary phrase and passive.

A phrase does not have complete content and tone, does not express an idea, and differs from a sentence, which is a syntactic unit. The modern demand requires a revision of the teaching of the language both in terms of organization and content. It is known that the content of the updated language education is aimed at forming and developing the skills of creativity, independent thinking, and the ability to correctly express the product of thought in oral, written and oral forms in accordance with the speech framework. Modernization of the education system, like all areas of our life, remains one of the most urgent problems of today. Innovative creating an educational environment, ensuring its full compliance with international standards is an important factor in the successful socialization of our youth to the rapidly changing social life today. The effective solution of this task, in turn, requires modernization of the educational process as a whole system. One of the most important parameters of the innovative direction of education is to ensure that students, as subjects of

the educational process, become creators of their own activities. Achieving this goal, in turn, requires students to organize cooperative work in groups, small groups, and pairs. Each interactive method is used to improve the quality of education, to increase its effectiveness, to establish mutual cooperation between teachers and students, students and groups of students, as well as the team, ideological and has great potential in creating the necessary conditions and environment for achieving spiritual unity, striving for a single goal, realizing the inner potential of each learner, and manifesting as a person. The study of word combinations is of great theoretical and practical interest, contributes to the identification of the structure, types of connection between the components of not only the word combinations themselves and their semantic-syntactic relations, but also, mainly, further study of the sentence as the main unit of syntax. They are an exceptionally productive means of expressing the most diverse shades of lexical and grammatical meanings. Their description is important and meaningful in the syntax of a phrase.

According to the definition of the Academic Grammar of the Russian Language, "The phrase is included in the message unit as its component, it must be present in it or extending it, expanding it. The property of the phrase to be included in the message unit, to participate in the formation of a simple and complex sentence, to function as a unit, - all its linguistic characteristics belong to the field of phrase syntax". From this it is clear that in order to study a sentence, it is first necessary to study its components - phrases. A comprehensive analysis of the features of one of the types of substantive definitive phrases, the identification of all types and relationships between the constituent components, I think, will to some extent fill this gap, deepen our understanding of the phrase, of the language itself, since, according to academician V.V. Vinogradova, "In the rules of word combinations, in the patterns of formation of different types and types of phrases, the national specificity of the language is clearly manifested". Such work will make it possible to find out how the speaker connects the words he has chosen to express certain thoughts.

This work is devoted to the study of the system of substantive phrases existing in the modern Russian language: the compatibility of different parts of speech with a noun, determining the productivity of different types of phrases, identifying the correlation of lexical and syntactic meanings between members of such phrases. The subject of this work is one of the types of the most productive non-independent syntactic units - substantive attributive phrases in the modern language. The paper deals with the theory of phrases and describes all types of substantive non-possessive phrases in this language. The main purpose of the study is to study and describe the main models of substantive attributive phrases in the modern Russian language, which are a group of determinative ones. To achieve this goal, it is necessary to comprehensively solve a number of specific theoretical and practical problems in three areas:

1) clarify the issue of the nature of a free phrase, consider general questions of vocabulary and grammar - the relationship between the phrase and other language units (word - analysis of cases of transition of syntactic phrases into lexical units - phrase - sentence); consider the types of connection in phrases and clarify the content of the term "harmonization" in relation to the languages;

2) to identify structural models of substantive phrases in the modern Russian language, to establish types and subspecies of substantive phrases based on the morphological characteristics of the core and dependent components, that is, on the basis of its particular morphological categories;

3) consider the ways and means of forming these phrases and lexical and grammatical relations established between the combined components; determine the degree of productivity and usage of substantive phrases;

4) describe the lexical and grammatical meanings and shades of meanings characteristic of different subspecies of substantive phrases and depending on the lexical and grammatical characteristics of the core and dependent components.

Although interactive methods, by their nature, provide a certain level of efficiency in the implementation of educational or educational goals, however, each of them has different opportunities to ensure productivity in the educational or educational process. Therefore, when choosing interactive methods, teachers should pay attention to the studied topic, problem or issue that needs to be solved. If the age, psychological characteristics, level of worldview, and life experiences of learners are taken into account when using interactive methods, its effectiveness will increase. This requires teachers to have professional skills, competence, knowledge, sensitivity and intuition.

A word combination is formed from the connection of independent words in speech. to be a phrase:

- 1) there must be at least two independent words;
- 2) these words must be semantically compatible;
- 3) one of the words must follow the other, be subordinate;
- 4) auxiliary and auxiliary words should connect independent words.
- 5) Conjunctions and possessive adverbs and auxiliaries (also tone) serve to connect words in the structure of word combinations.

A non-predicative conjunction always consists of two members, one of which is subject and the other is ruler. In a predicative conjunction, its governing member is usually placed first, and the subordinate member is placed after. The important difference is that in the predicative conjunction, both of its members are represented by a word form, and both of them are formed as a syntactic part (possessive, participle). In non-predicative conjunctions, its subordinate member is often represented by a word form, so only this member is formed as a syntactic fragment (for example, a complement). Non-predicative conjunctions (these are also referred to as conjunctions) are classified differently, one of them is classification based on the syntactic essence of the subordinate member, in which conjunctions such as qualifying conjunctions, complementing conjunctions, and case conjunctions are distinguished. Subordinate member of compounds (adjective, complement, case) used to be a secondary part of the sentence, in the following years it is interpreted as a spreading part. In fact, it is appropriate to talk about the expression of a syntactic fragment with various conjunctions, in addition to the word form, rather than the spread of the syntactic fragment. In the construction of a sentence, it is a separate issue that a part belongs to another sentence as a whole, and in solving this problem, there is no need for the concept of a spreading part to be a part of a part at the beginning. Complementary compounds are essentially the same in Russian and Uzbek languages.

The meaning of the lexeme determines the syntactic form of the connected complement. Two types of filler are distinguished: indirect filler and instrumental filler. Adverbial compounds are essentially the same in Russian and Uzbek languages. There are two types of syntactic relationship between the case and the case: 1) If there is no change of form in the case, the case is connected to the case by the conjugation method; 2) in the function of a predicate, if a

word form formed with a certain agreement or an auxiliary (preposition in Russian) comes, it is connected with the control method. Adjective compounds differ sharply in Russian and Uzbek languages. Adjectives in the Russian language are divided into two: adapting and non-adaptive adjectives. An adjective that deserves to be regarded as an adjective in its literal sense, that is, both grammatically and semantically, is an adaptive adjective. Because in the function of such an adjective, the lexeme of the category representing the sign of the object comes, and it receives a grammatical indicator in accordance with the grammatical form of the qualified noun and changes accordingly. In the Russian language, the subordinate member (adjective) of a compound with an adjective receives a grammatical indicator depending on the volume member (qualification), a proportional change occurs between the grammatical indicators. But within the compound, the grammatical form of neither the governing member nor the subordinate member is clear, the members of such a compound acquire a specific grammatical form in speech. The language has a pattern of such an adjectival combination: (base + completion) which completions (by itself, which lexemes) participate in this pattern becomes clear only in speech. So, in the Russian language, the subordinate member of the adjective compound does not form grammatically within the compound; the governing member of such a combination (and the original combination itself) is completely grammatically formed in speech.

Therefore, even in such devices, the relative clause in the subject matter is proportionally added to the base of the word form in the function of the referent from the point of view of the person. As long as the relation is not between grammatical indicators, such a syntactic grammatical relation cannot be called adaptation. So, in some forms of the referential compound, adaptation in number occurs or proportionality in number disappears, and in other forms, coordination in number occurs. The Uzbek language does not have regular adaptation laws like the Russian language. Usually in the Uzbek language, it is considered that the participle is compatible. Therefore, even when the subject clause is dropped, the subordinate clause can keep its previous form. can be used with a singular indicator. In the Russian language, there are mainly two types of conjugation: the first is the conjugation of the participle with the possessor in gender, number and person, and the second is the conjugation of the determiner with the definite noun in gender, number and agreement. In Russian, there are also complete and incomplete forms of adaptation.

In the Russian language, adaptation is mainly in two types of combinations: the first is the adaptation of the participle with the possessive in the stem, number and person, and the second is the adaptation of the determiner with the definite article in the stem, number and agreement. There are complete and incomplete forms of adaptation in Russian. In the management of the Russian language, requires that the governing word (often a verb) is followed by a subordinate word in a certain agreement, without a preposition or with a preposition. In addition, some groups of prepositions in Russian require nouns to be in a certain instrumental agreement.

References:

1. Arutyunov A. R. Theory and practice of creating a Russian language textbook for foreigners. - M.: Russian language, 1990. - 168 p.

2. Kapitonova T. I., Moskovkin L. V., Shchukin A. N. Methods and technologies of teaching Russian as a foreign language / ed. A.N. Schukin. — M.: Rus. lang. courses, 2008. - 312 p.
3. New technologies in teaching a foreign language. — http://www.langinfo.ru/index.php?sect_id=
4. Ostapenko V.I. Teaching Russian grammar to foreigners at the initial stage. - 3rd ed., Rev. — M.: Rus. yaz., 1987. -144 p.
5. Skorina M. S. Interactive methods of teaching a foreign language. — http://www.rusnauka.com/8_NPE_2007/Philologia/20441.doc.htm

